

Impact of Socio-demographic Factors on Childhood Trauma, Aggression, Self-harm, and Personality Traits among Tribal Young Adults in Tripura

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The present study seeks to examine the influence of socio-demographic variables on childhood trauma, aggression, self-harm and personality among the young Bru tribal community. The existing literature highlights the prevalence of childhood trauma in India, but the research highlighting the association of socio-demographic factors with the psychological variables is limited, especially for particularly vulnerable tribes that suffer the structural disadvantages, poverty, marginalization, and insecurities. In order to address this gap, the present study was conducted with 187 (117 males & 53 females) young Bru community. The sample was collected through a multistage sampling technique from the Gomati district of Tripura. The psychological variables were measured using the Self-Harm Inventory (Sansone, Wiederman, & Sansone, 1998), Childhood Trauma Questionnaire (CTQ-SFBernstein & Fink, 1998), NEO-Five Factor Inventory (Costa & McCrae, 1992), and Bush and Perry Aggression Questionnaire (BPAQ: Buss & Perry, 1992), along with the socio-demographic profile. The findings of the present study reveal that the only demographic variable that impacts childhood trauma, aggression, self-harm, extraversion, and agreeableness, as personality dimensions, is education. Other socio-demographic variables do not show any association with the aforementioned psychological variables. Therefore, the present study highlights the power of education to mitigate prevailing disparities and foster individuals' mental health.

Keywords: Childhood trauma, aggression, self-harm, personality dimension, tribal community

Forced displacement resulting from armed conflict and ethnic clashes affects millions of individuals worldwide, with internally displaced persons (IDPs) representing one of the most vulnerable populations. IDPs are the most vulnerable people because they are exposed to traumatic events like armed attacks, forced relocation, destruction of property, and witnessing death, which can significantly lead to mental health problems like post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, anxiety disorders, and somatic symptoms (World Health Organization [WHO], 2019). Children and adolescents are particularly-vulnerable, as disrupted education, health care and exposure to violence negatively affect psychosocial development and mental health outcomes (Scharpf et al., 2020). Furthermore, the displaced tribal communities are found to be more vulnerable due to longstanding socioeconomic marginalization, geographic isolation, and limited access to culturally appropriate mental health facilities (Usha & Yoganandham, 2024).

While these structural susceptibilities-form mental health

outcomes across displaced communities, the impact of internal displacement also varies significantly across different stages of the life path (Tyrrell & Kraftl, 2016). Young adulthood is one of the most critical periods in this regard. Erikson (1968) in his psychosocial development theory identifies it as critical developmental stage characterized by identity formation, emotional regulation, and personality consolidation. However, experience to violence during childhood and adolescence can significantly disturb these developmental processes by impairing emotional regulation capacities and maladaptive cognitive schemas (Shonkoff et al., 2012). Empirical research consistently demonstrates that exposure to armed conflict can lead to long-term psychological problems like maladaptive personality traits, heightened aggression, and childhood trauma (Dube et al., 2001; Felitti et al., 1998; Widom et al., 2009).

Childhood trauma has been associated with changes in personality development, particularly in traits linked to emotional instability, impulsivity, and interpersonal distrust (Rosenman & Rodgers, 2006). Longitudinal studies' findings demonstrate that early maltreatment predicts maladaptive personality trajectories into adulthood, as early adverse experiences sabotage secure attachment formation and lead to emotional dysregulation and interpersonal instability, which in turn increase the risk of self-injurious behaviours (Bowlby, 1969; van der Kolk & Fisler, 1994; Widom et al., 2006). Moreover, research on young adults revealed that individuals who experienced childhood abuse are more prone to aggression and self-harm behaviour, which is further mediated by amplified stress reactivity and problems in affect regulation (Andersson et al., 2022; Dube et al., 2001). According to the developmental perspective, trauma erodes regulatory systems involved in affect modulation and impulse control, which increases

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vulnerability to both aggression and self-harm (Shonkoff et al., 2012). This indicates that the relationship between childhood and psychological trauma in young adulthood is both direct and indirect. Trauma may disrupt developmental processes and contribute to maladaptive personality features and emotional vulnerability, which are associated with an increased risk of aggression and self-harm in young adults (Turner et al., 2018).

Other than insidious and direct effects of childhood trauma, socio-demographic factors such as age, gender, educational level, marital status, income level, and family structure play an important role in aggression, self-harm and traumatic experience (Lund et al., 2010; Olff, 2017; Tolin & Foa, 2008). Research indicates that lower socioeconomic status and limited educational attainment are associated with heightened psychological distress due to reduced access to mental health services, social support, and adaptive coping opportunities (Lund et al., 2010). Gender has a moderating role on trauma responses. Research suggests that females are more likely to develop PTSD and exhibit internalizing symptoms such as depression and self-harm, whereas males are more likely to exhibit externalizing behaviors, including aggression (Olff, 2017; Tolin & Foa, 2008). Culturally embedded gender norms within the tribal and marginalized group too shape the expression and management of distress that may further influence the help-seeking behaviour and emotional regulation patterns.

Although a vast body of literatures is conducted on the mental health of conflict-affected populations, a significant gap remains in research specifically on the tribal young adults who were internally displaced due to war and conflict. Studies have consistently reported high rates of psychological distress in conflict-affected populations (Charlson et al., 2019). However, research on the unique socio-cultural vulnerabilities of tribal IDPs such as cultural disruption, geographic isolation, and limited access to mental health care services (Usha & Yoganandham, 2024) is underexplored. Furthermore, though childhood trauma is associated with self-harm (Dube et al., 2001), aggression (Widom et al., 2006), and maladaptive personality traits, the relationship between socio-demographic variables, experience of trauma, personality dimension, and behavioral outcomes were inadequately examined within tribal IDPs contexts. This gap reinforces the need for unified, context-specific research models to better understand psychological risk pathways among marginalized and displaced young adults. Therefore, the present study aims to investigate the impact of socio-demographic factors on childhood trauma among Bru, young adults who had experienced armed conflict during their early childhood.

Method

Participants

The present study sample consisted of 187 tribal young adults (117 males & 53 females) from the Bru community, a formerly internally displaced population that has since undergone permanent resettlement in Tripura, India. The participants ages range from 24 to 36 years ($M=30$), representing the country's young adult population. A purposive sampling technique was utilized for sample selection. The following table represents the sociodemographic characteristics of the study sample (Table 1).

Table 1

Socio-demographic Profile of the Participants

Variable	Category	N	%
Gender	Male	116	62%
	Female	71	38%
Age	24-30	127	68%
	31-36	60	32%
Marital status	Married	134	71.7%
	Unmarried	53	28.3%
Occupation	Unemployed	140	74.87%
	Daily Wage worker	9	4.81%
	Farmer	7	3.74%
	Self employed	15	8.02%
	Student	6	3.21%
	Government employee	4	2.14%
	Private sector employee	1	0.53%
	Homemaker	2	1.07%
	Other	3	1.60%
Education	No formal education	15	8.0%
	Primary	18	9.6%
	Secondary	106	56.7%
	Higher secondary	29	15.5%
	Graduate	16	8.6%
Birth order	Post graduate and above	3	1.6%
	1st	49	26.2%
	2nd	58	31.0%
	3rd	48	25.7%
	4th	21	11.2%
Family Income	5th	11	5.9%
	Less than 5000	162	86.6%
	5000-10000	23	12.3%
Family type	10000-20000	2	1.1%
	Nuclear	34	18.2%
	Joint	103	55.1%
	Extended	50	26.7%

Measures

Socio-demographic Information: A basic information schedule was developed to collect all the necessary demographic information from the subjects. Data includes information of gender, age, education, area of living, migration, family income, family environment, health profile, etc.

Childhood Trauma Questionnaire Short Form (CTQ-SF; Bernstein & Fink, 1998): The CTQ-SF (Bernstein & Fink, 1998) consists of 28 items that assess retrospective childhood maltreatment across five domains: a) emotional abuse b) physical abuse c) sexual abuse d) emotional neglect e) physical neglect. The responses are recorded on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 being never true to 5 as very often true. The tool also comprises Minimization/Denial subscale to assess for possible underreporting or response bias. It measures whether the individual has a history of abuse and neglect of the five domains designed for the tool and their nature of frequency. Cronbach's alpha's score for all the factors' reliability ranged from 0.79 to 0.94 and the test-retest yielded its stability correlation as 0.88 for a period of 2-6 months (Bernstein & Fink, 1998).

Self-Harm Inventory (Sansone, Wiederman, & Sansone, 1998): It is a 20-item self-report instrument designed to assess lifetime self-harm behaviours. Participants respond to each item with a "Yes"

or "No," indicating whether they have engaged in specific behaviours (e.g., cutting, burning, or staying in emotionally abusive relationships). A total score of 5 or more suggests a significant risk of self-harming behavior and potential features of borderline personality disorder. A meta-analysis on mixed population (Sansone et al., 2015) resulted in the internal consistency as 0.85 (Cronbach's alpha).

Bush and Perry Aggression Questionnaire (BPAQ: Buss & Perry, 1992): It is a 29-item self-report measure used to assess aggression in adults aged 18 years and above. It comprised of four components: physical aggression (engagement in physical harm), verbal aggression (arguments & confrontations), anger (emotional arousal such as irritability & frustration), and hostility (cognitive feelings of resentment and suspicion). These subscales together provide a comprehensive assessment of behavioral, affective, and cognitive aspects of aggression. The Buss and Perry Aggression Questionnaire (BPAQ; Buss & Perry, 1992) has demonstrated good reliability ($\alpha = .89$; test-retest $r = .80$) and strong construct validity (Harris, 1995).

NEO Five-Factor Inventory (Costa & McCrae, 1992): It is a 60-item self-report instrument designed to assess the five major personality domains (neuroticism, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, & conscientiousness). Participants respond using a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (*Strongly Disagree*) to 5 (*Strongly Agree*). The instrument demonstrates internal consistency reliability, with

coefficients reported as 0.83 for conscientiousness and 0.80 for neuroticism. The subscales for agreeableness and Extraversion showed reliability coefficients of 0.60 and 0.58, respectively.

Procedure

The ethical norms of the research were followed in order to collect the data from the subjects. Before beginning the data collection, a proper rapport was established with the subjects and then they were asked to fill up the consent form. Only those subjects who were voluntarily willing to take part in the study were selected for the study. Data were collected from the subjects individually by survey method and were analyzed quantitatively.

Data Analysis

After data collection was completed, all questionnaires were exported to Microsoft Excel for initial coding and preliminary analysis. The frequencies were carefully calculated for all the demographic variables. Statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS v27. The multiple regression was performed to see the impact of demographic variables on psychological variables. To test the robustness of the results bootstrapping was also performed.

Results

Table 2

Multiple Regression Predicting Childhood Trauma Status from Socio-demographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	73.563	6.327		11.627	<.001	61.078	86.048
Marital status	1.779	1.830	.072	.972	.332	-1.833	5.391
Gender	-2.207	1.661	-.094	-1.329	.186	-5.484	1.070
Age	-2.665	1.728	-.111	-1.543	.125	-6.074	.744
Birth order	-.088	.676	-.009	-.130	.897	-1.422	1.246
Education	-3.797	.804	-.347	-4.721	<.001	-5.384	-2.210
occupation	.073	.511	.011	.142	.887	-.936	1.081
Income	-3.979	2.400	-.135	-1.658	.099	-8.715	.757
Family	-1.159	1.185	-.069	-.978	.329	-3.497	1.180

Note. $R^2 = .167$, Adjusted $R^2 = .129$, $F(8, 178) = 4.452$, $p < .001$, B = unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B = standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Graph 1

The Normal P-P Plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 2 represents the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic variables (gender, age, marital status, education, occupation, family income, birth order, & family environment) on childhood trauma among the

tribal young adults. The overall model was significant, $F(8,178) = 4.452, p < .001$, and accounted for approximately 16.7% of the variance in childhood trauma ($R^2 = .167, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .129$). Education ($\beta = -.347, p < .001$) contributed to predicting childhood trauma.

Table 3
Multiple Regression Predicting Aggression from Socio-demographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	81.129	7.352		11.035	<.001	66.621	95.637
Marital status	-1.995	2.127	-.069	-.938	.350	-6.192	2.202
Gender	-.700	1.930	-.026	-.363	.717	-4.509	3.108
Age	2.362	2.007	.084	1.176	.241	-1.600	6.323
Birth order	1.513	.786	.134	1.926	.056	-.037	3.063
Education	4.989	.935	.390	5.338	<.001	3.144	6.833
occupation	.099	.594	.013	.166	.868	-1.073	1.271
Income	-7.231	2.789	-.211	-2.593	.010	-12.735	-1.727
Family	.994	1.377	.051	.722	.472	-1.724	3.711

Note. $R^2 = .173, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .136, F(8, 178) = 4.664, p < .001$, B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B= standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Graph 2
The Normal P-P Plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 4
Multiple Regression Predicting Self-harm from Socio-demographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	4.646	.868		5.351	<.001	2.933	6.360
Marital status	.276	.251	.077	1.097	.274	-.220	.771
Gender	-.308	.228	-.092	-1.351	.178	-.758	.142
Age	-.338	.237	-.098	-1.427	.155	-.806	.130
Birth order	-.262	.093	-.188	-2.821	.005	-.445	-.079
Education	-.698	.110	-.443	-6.319	<.001	-.915	-.480
Occupation	-.002	.070	-.003	-.034	.973	-.141	.136
Income	.254	.329	.060	.772	.441	-.396	.904
Family	-.307	.163	-.127	-1.891	.060	-.628	.013

Note. $R^2 = .239, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .205, F(8, 178) = 7.000, p < .001$, B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B= standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Table 3 presents the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic variables on aggression among the Bru community. The overall model was found to be significant, $F(8, 178) = 4.664, p < .001$, accounting for approximately 17.3% of the variance ($R^2 = .173$, Adjusted $R^2 = .136$). Education ($\beta = .390, p < .001$) was found to be a significant positive predictor of aggression.

Table 4 shows the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic variables on self-harm among the tribal young adults. The overall model was found to be significant, $F(7, 179) = 7.000, p < .01$, accounting for approximately 23.9% of the variance ($R^2 = .239$, Adjusted $R^2 = .205$). Education ($\beta = -.443, p < .001$) was found to be a significant predictor of self-harm behaviour.

Graph 3

The Normal P-P Plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 5

Multiple Regression Predicting Neuroticism Dimension of Personality from Socio-demographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	48.558	3.027		16.039	<.001	42.583	54.532
Marital status	-.968	.876	-.087	-1.105	.271	-2.696	.761
Gender	-.781	.795	-.075	-.982	.327	-2.349	.788
Age	.207	.827	.019	.250	.803	-1.424	1.838
Birth order	.136	.324	.032	.420	.675	-.502	.774
Education	.356	.385	.073	.926	.356	-.403	1.116
Occupation	.249	.245	.087	1.019	.310	-.233	.732
Income	-.128	1.148	-.010	-.112	.911	-2.395	2.138
Family	.904	.567	.120	1.594	.113	-.215	2.023

Note. $R^2 = .042$, Adjusted $R^2 = -.001$, $F(8, 178) = .984, p > .05$, B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B= standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Table 5 shows the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic variables on neuroticism among the tribal young adult. The results indicated that the overall was not significant, $F(8, 178) = .984, p > .05$. Therefore, there was no significant impact of socio-demographic variables on neuroticism dimension of personality.

Table 6 represents the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic

variables on extraversion among young adults. The overall model was not significant, $F(8, 178) = 3.198, p > .05$. Therefore, this indicates that collectively the sets of predictors do not explain the significantly significant amount of variance in extraversion. However, though overall model is weak but education showed ($\beta = .329, p < .001$) was found to be significant positive predictors of extraversion while controlling the other variables.

Graph 4

The Normal P-P plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 6

Multiple Regression Predicting Extraversion from Socio-demographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	50.074	2.664		18.794	<.001	44.816	55.331
Marital status	-1.161	.771	-.114	-1.506	.134	-2.628	.360
Gender	1.427	.699	.149	2.040	.043	.047	2.807
Age	.121	.728	.012	.167	.868	-1.314	1.557
Birth order	-.103	.285	-.026	-.363	.717	-.665	.459
Education	1.482	.339	.329	4.376	<.001	.814	2.151
Occupation	-.004	.215	-.001	-.017	.986	-.428	.421
Income	.631	1.011	.052	.624	.533	-1.364	2.625
Family	.082	.499	.012	.163	.870	-.903	1.066

Note. $R^2 = .355$, Adjusted $R^2 = .126$, $F(8, 178) = 3.198$, $p > .05$, B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B= standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Graph 5

The Normal P-P plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 7

Multiple Regression Predicting Openness Dimension of Personality from Sociodemographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	48.367	3.173		15.244	<.001	42.106	54.629
Marital status	.905	.918	.077	.986	.326	-.907	2.716
Gender	-1.026	.833	-.093	-1.232	.220	-2.669	.618
Age	-.985	.866	-.087	-1.137	.257	-2.695	.724
Birth order	-.071	.339	-.015	-.208	.836	-.740	.599
Education	-.925	.403	-.179	-2.294	.023	-1.721	-.129
Occupation	.183	.256	.060	.715	.476	-.323	.689
Income	.060	1.204	.004	.050	.960	-2.315	2.435
Family	.786	.594	.099	1.322	.188	-.387	1.959

Note. $R^2 = .054$, Adjusted $R^2 = .012$, $F(8, 178) = 1.274$, $p > .05$, B = unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B = standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Table 7 represents the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic variables on the openness dimension of personality among the tribal youth. The

results indicated that the overall model was not significant, $F(8, 178) = 1.274$, $p > .05$. This indicates that there is no significant impact of socio-demographic variables on openness dimension of personality.

Graph 6

The Normal P-P plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 8

Multiple Regression Predicting Agreeableness Dimension of Personality from Socio-demographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	49.250	2.611		18.866	<.001	44.098	54.401
Marital status	1.264	.755	.126	1.673	.096	-.227	2.754
Gender	.525	.685	.056	.767	.444	-.827	1.878
Age	.131	.713	.013	.184	.854	-1.276	1.538
Birth order	-.402	.279	-.103	-1.442	.151	-.953	.148
Education	-1.406	.332	-.317	-4.236	<.001	-2.061	-.751
Occupation	.019	.211	.007	.090	.929	-.397	.435
Income	-1.203	.990	-.101	-1.215	.226	-3.158	.751
Family	.092	.489	.014	.189	.850	-.872	1.057

Note. $R^2 = .135$, Adjusted $R^2 = .096$, $F(8, 178) = 3.481$, $p < .001$, B = unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B = standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Table 8 represents the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic variables on agreeableness among the tribal young adults. The overall model was found to be significant, $F(8, 178) = 3.481, p < .001$, accounting for

approximately 13.5% of the variance ($R^2 = .135, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .096$). Education ($\beta = -.317, p < .001$) contributed to predicting Agreeableness.

Graph 7

The Normal P-P plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 9

Multiple Regression Predicting Conscientiousness Dimension of Personality from Sociodemographic Variables

Predictor Variables	B	SE B	β	t	p	Lower bound	Upper bound
Constant	43.365	3.575		12.129	<.001	36.309	50.420
Marital status	-1.123	1.034	-.085	-1.085	.279	-3.164	.919
Gender	.116	.938	.009	.123	.902	-1.736	1.968
Age	.744	.976	.058	.762	.447	-1.182	2.671
Birth order	.326	.382	.063	.853	.395	-.428	1.080
Education	1.147	.455	.196	2.524	.012	.250	2.044
Occupation	-.094	.289	-.027	-.325	.745	-.664	.476
Income	1.479	1.356	.094	1.090	.277	-1.198	4.156
Family	.854	.670	.095	1.275	.204	-.468	2.175

Note. $R^2 = .067, \text{Adjusted } R^2 = .025, F(8, 178) = 1.063, p > .05$, B= unstandardized regression coefficient, SE B= standard error, β = standardized coefficient

Graph 8

The Normal P-P plot of Standardized Residuals Indicated that the Residual Followed a Near Normal Distribution

Table 9 shows the results of a multiple regression analysis conducted to examine the impact of socio-demographic variables on conscientiousness among tribal youth. The results indicated that the overall model was not significant, $F(8, 178) = 1.063, p > .05$. This indicates that there is no significant impact of socio-demographic variables on the agreeableness dimension of personality.

Discussion

The present study examines the influence of socio-demographic factors (age, gender, marital status, birth order, education, occupation, income, & family background) on childhood trauma, aggression, self-harm, and personality traits among tribal young adults from the Bru community who were formerly internally displaced and are now permanently settled in Tripura, Northeast India. The findings indicate that education significantly influences childhood trauma, aggression, self-harm, and personality (extraversion & agreeableness).

Education plays a crucial role in mitigating the psychological and behavioral consequences of childhood trauma, aggression, and self-harm through multiple protective and developmental mechanisms. Research indicates that education is not a cure for all social problems, but it can reduce the impact of trauma by functioning as a structured, stable, and supportive environment (Haris et al., 2017). Educational institutions provide safety and supervision, which are particularly important for children who are exposed to adverse childhood experiences. Schafer (2024) reported that a large number of students who have experienced a significant amount of trauma emphasize the importance of trauma-informed educational practices that help teachers to recognize and respond to trauma-related distress. Such practices include emotional and routine check-ins, and supportive teacher-student relationships, all of which help to create psychologically safe learning spaces. Susanto and Sulastris (2025) further validate the effectiveness of psychological interventions delivered within educational contexts as it enhances coping skills, strengthening of emotions, and resilience. In relation to aggression, Drysdale (2019) finds a positive association between childhood trauma and aggressive behavior, while also emphasizes that educational experience can serve as an important protective factor. Specifically, school-based programs that promote emotional awareness, and teaches impulse control, and also develop conflict-resolution skills which mitigate the expression of aggression, and reduce the likelihood that trauma can lead to externalizing behaviors. Also, education not only imparts knowledge but also functions as a structured environment that promotes social and emotional regulation, which directly influenced the aggressive tendencies. Couldrey et al. (2010) identify emotion dysregulation as a mediator between childhood abuse and aggression, which suggests that educational environments systematically teach emotion regulation strategies that can disrupt this pathway. Education also impacts self-harm through indirect protective mechanisms. Zabaraukaitė and Lesinskiene (2025) in their research found that unpleasant childhood experiences can notably amplify the risk of self-harm and suicidal behavior, while positive childhood experiences found to buffer this risk. Schools can offer positive experiences through peer relationship, extracurricular activities, and mentoring relationships. Lang and Sharma-Patel (2011) further suggested that therapeutic approaches such as Dialectical Behavior Therapy, Trauma-Focused Cognitive Behavioral Therapy, and Acceptance and Commitment therapy should often be used in school

settings, which are effective in informing trauma-related developmental deviations that contribute to self-injury. Research also suggests that education impacts trauma, aggression, and self-harm behaviour by offering stable environments, early identification of distress, emotional skill development, resilience enhancement, and access to targeted psychosocial interventions (Drysdale, 2019).

Education also has the potential to influence personality development, particularly the dimensions of extraversion and agreeableness, through structured social reinforcement and developmental processes. According to Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory, behaviors are internalized and repeated only when they are observed and positively reinforced. In academic settings, students are often encouraged to participate in group activities such as discussion, presentation, and projects that will engage them in peer interaction. These behaviors tend to be socially rewarded through academic recognition, teacher approval, and peer acceptance. Gradually, this repeated reinforcement strengthens sociability, assertiveness, and verbal expressiveness, which reflect the core features of extraversion. Additionally, it is consistent with Erik Erikson's psychosocial developmental stages, adolescence and young adulthood, characterized by identity formation and intimacy development, respectively. Thereby, to reinforce outward engagement and interpersonal competence, educational institutions are providing structural opportunities for young adults to explore social relationships, build relationships, and consolidate identity. Through these experiences, schools may not only support academic growth but also actively shape personality traits associated with extraverted behaviour (Dahmann & Anger, 2014). Education not only contributes to agreeableness by promoting cooperation, empathy, and prosocial norms (Kassenboehmer, Leung, & Schurer, 2018) but also, through collaborative assignments, rule-following, and exposure to diverse approaches, students learn to value different viewpoints and engage in constructive conflict resolution. Furthermore, moral and ethical discussions within educational contexts also enhance perspective-taking and empathy, reinforcing agreeable tendencies. Thus, education not only transmits academic knowledge but also shapes behavioral patterns through repeated social interaction, normative reinforcement, and socio-emotional skill development, which contributes to higher levels of extraversion and agreeableness (Kassenboehmer, Leung, & Schurer, 2018).

Conversely, the absence of significant associations between neuroticism, openness, and conscientiousness and socio-demographic variables can be understood through the Five-Factor Theory proposed by Paul Costa and Robert McCrae. This theory suggests that core personality traits are biologically rooted and demonstrate stability across adulthood, remaining relatively consistent and independent of external influences. Whereas environmental factors may play an important role in shaping the characteristic adaptations such as goals, attitudes, or coping strategies but they are less likely to alter basic dispositional traits. Empirical support for these findings is provided by Roberts et al. (2006), whose meta-analysis found that conscientiousness and neuroticism change slightly with a person's life, but these changes are usually small, especially in early adulthood. Although gender differences in neuroticism are constantly observed but are modest in magnitude and may not yield statistically significant results within relatively homogeneous samples (Costa et al., 2001). Additionally,

when participants fall under a restricted age range and similar socioeconomic contexts, variability in socio-demographic factors may be insufficient to produce detectable differences in stable personality traits. Therefore, neuroticism, openness, and conscientiousness may operate and largely independently of structural demographic characteristics in young adulthood. These findings also align with the trait theory, suggesting that while education can influence trauma-related outcomes and the behavioral expression of certain socially reinforced traits, core dispositional dimensions remain relatively consistent and less susceptible to variation based on socio-demographic status.

Conclusion, Limitation, and Suggestion

The study explored how socio-demographic factors affect childhood trauma, aggression, personality traits, and self-harm among tribal young adults from the Bru community. Childhood trauma was predicted by education indicating that these groups differ in confidence and vulnerability. Aggression, self-harm as well as extraversion and agreeableness dimensions of personality were also shaped by education. However, neuroticism openness and conscientiousness dimensions of personality were not predicted by socio-demographic factors.

This study has certain limitations, primarily due to the smaller sample size. Additionally, the measurement scales used for psychological variables were a self-reported survey questionnaire, which may influence response patterns due to factors such as social desirability, fatigue, and boredom. Apart from all this, there may be some other factor such as the population was taken from one district only. Either controlling for or considering these factors in the study may further increase the predictive value of socio-demographic factors on psychological variables.

Summing up, the findings broaden the applicability of socio-demographic factors as a predictor of psychological outcomes. Future research should use diverse cultures to deepen understanding and should explore other socio-demographic variables that contribute to childhood trauma and mental health in the targeted population. Also, the study can use a mixed-methods research design to provide richer and more comprehensive results. Integrating both methods could give voice to participants' - lived experiences and increase the depth of future studies.

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